

Gain-Invariant Retinal Arterial Velocity Waveform Shape Metrics from Beat-Resolved Laser Doppler Holography Under Reversible Moderate Intraocular Pressure Elevation

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Abstract: Retinal laser Doppler holography at 37,000 frames per second yields beat-resolved arterial velocity waveforms. We introduce three gain-invariant pulse-shape metrics and show they separate baseline from reversible moderate intraocular-pressure elevation in seconds-long acquisitions.

1. Motivation

Beat-resolved retinal arterial velocity waveforms encode pulsatility, damping, and compliance-related signatures of the microcirculation. However, translating waveform information to longitudinal and multi-site studies is hindered by imperfect absolute calibration: multiplicative gain fluctuations can arise even within a session due to small changes in eye alignment, tear film, optical throughput, speckle statistics, and background subtraction/segmentation variability. We target dimensionless waveform-shape descriptors that are robust, auditable, and transportable when the velocity $v(t)$ is known only up to an unknown scaling factor g .

2. Ultrafast retinal laser Doppler holography

We use a real-time Doppler holography prototype (Mach–Zehnder interferometer, $\lambda = 852$ nm) delivering near-infrared illumination in a diffuse Maxwellian-view configuration and recording fundus interferograms at ~ 37 kHz on a high-speed camera. Hologram reconstruction and Doppler processing via open-source software provide vessel contrasts and automated extraction of arterial velocity waveforms from seconds-long acquisitions.

3. Intraocular pressure provocation protocol and beat locking

Moderate, reversible intraocular pressure (IOP) elevation from 12 mmHg to 20 mmHg is induced by gentle ocular indentation through the closed eyelid, creating a short, within-session perfusion-pressure challenge. Acquisitions are grouped as baseline (B), indentation (I), and recovery (B). Beats are segmented directly from the arterial velocity waveform, using the time of maximum upstroke (peak dv/dt) as a common origin, and each beat is mapped onto $t \in [0, T]$ (upstroke-to-upstroke), where T is the beat period.

4. Deterministic band-limited waveform synthesis

For each beat, we compute the DC component V_0 and complex harmonic coefficients V_n at cardiac harmonics $n\omega_0$ with $\omega_0 = 2\pi/T$. We define a low-pass representation by reverse synthesis (DC + first 12 harmonics):

$$v(t) = V_0 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{12} \Re[V_n e^{in\omega_0 t}], \quad t \in [0, T]. \quad (1)$$

This explicit band-limiting stabilizes extrema, integrals, and moments used by the pulse-shape metrics.

5. Three gain-invariant pulse-shape metrics

We construct robust arterial velocity waveform shape metrics computed per beat from aligned band-limited signals.

Fig. 1. Beat-resolved arterial velocity waveforms: raw (dots) vs band-limited (line) reconstruction. Each panel overlays all beats from a single acquisition after mapping each beat to a common within-cycle time axis ($t \in [0, \bar{T}]$, where \bar{T} is the mean beat period of the acquisition), so that inter-beat shape variability can be compared directly. Both panels use the same y-axis range (mm/s) to enable direct visual comparison of pulsatility and morphology between conditions. The right panel corresponds to the ocular-indentation condition and is highlighted with a light-blue background.

Fig. 2. Experiment alternating baseline/indentation: gain-invariant pulse-shape metrics. Each point shows the mean across beats within one acquisition file; whiskers show the beat-to-beat standard deviation. Epochs are labeled B (baseline) or I (indentation). Metrics are computed beat-by-beat.

(1) **Rectified centroid-time ratio.** We define moments $M_0 = \int_0^T v(t) dt$, $M_1 = \int_0^T v(t)t dt$, and

$$\frac{\tau_{M1}}{T} = \frac{M_1}{T M_0}, \quad (2)$$

a scale-free timing descriptor (gain cancels in the ratio).

(2) **Resistivity index.** With $v_{\max} = \max v(t)$ and $v_{\min} = \min v(t)$ on $[0, T]$,

$$\text{RI} = \frac{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}{v_{\max}}, \quad (3)$$

which is invariant under $v \mapsto gv$ (beats with $v_{\max} \approx 0$ are QC-flagged).

(3) **Early/late stroke-distance ratio.** Define velocity-time integrals $d_1 = \int_0^{T/2} v(t) dt$ and $d_2 = \int_{T/2}^T v(t) dt$, then

$$R_{\text{VTI}} = \frac{d_1}{d_2 + \varepsilon}, \quad (4)$$

with tiny ε only to prevent division by zero (gain cancels between numerator and denominator).

6. Results in a proof-of-concept dataset

In a single-subject (healthy volunteer), single-eye dataset with two within-session provocation sequences, indentation produces directionally consistent changes in all three descriptors: τ_{M1}/T decreases, while RI and R_{VTI} increase, separating baseline from indentation at the per-acquisition level.

7. Conclusion

A minimal trio of dimensionless, gain-invariant pulse-shape metrics computed beat-by-beat from deterministic harmonic synthesis provides a compact and auditable description of retinal arterial waveform morphology. In a reversible moderate-IOP challenge, the metrics separate baseline from indentation in seconds-long Doppler holography acquisitions, supporting scalable functional hemodynamics endpoints for larger studies in ocular hypertension/glaucoma and systemic microvascular dysfunction.